

What's Behind Many Green Orientation? Is it Green-washing?

Scientists have been overwhelmingly suggesting that climate change is a hard and pressing issue that needs to be concerned by the whole world (Mair, 2011). Conventional enterprises are forced to change into green enterprises, as it was seen as a strategy on how enterprises can reduce environmental impacts among businesses and the whole world, where green integration of an enterprise gives those enterprises a unique competitive advantage (Cao et al., 2019). A study from (Guo et al., 2020) reveals that supply chain learning has positive effects on Green radical innovation and Green incremental innovation. Where it is an important organizational behavior that an organization has, as the impact of Green entrepreneurial Orientation Is different on various situations, therefore it is conditional where Green entrepreneurial Orientation enhances the level of green innovation and firm orientation. As where it affects a firm's orientation, many firms try to associate themselves with eco green or even inter-organizational as it benefits them (Lin, Y., & Chen, H., 2018). The important point is that entrepreneurial orientation, Marketing strategies, and competitive market affects how firms react as where associating with inter-organizational not only gives advantage in the competitive market but also helps the firm to be able to capitalize the gap to create better market orientation (Pratono et al., 2019). The entrepreneur is one of the few key respects of in decision making of organizations where it is motivated by the competitive nuance in the market, yet studies found that there is a positive relationship of GEO on GSCM (Habib et al., 2020). The rising trends of environmental awareness, customers that are aware, are going to prefer the eco-friendly product (Jiang et al., 2018). But (Jiang et al., 2018) also argues that eco-friendly products and process innovation is the consequence of firms being able to learn as an organisation.

As many organisations are Pressured by shareholders to get a larger profit, some of them are in a position where they need to make a choice of whether to keep their image untarnished or fall into doing green-washing (Chen, Y.S., & Chang, C.H, 2013). Green-washing, also known as eco-bleaching, whitewash, eco-washing, green washing, green makeup or green image washing, is a form of advertisements towards the public that misleads in order to create massive benefit for the company (Ko et al., 2013). A large amount of company uses green-washing to shape the public perception into believing they don't use harmful materials where it maximizes their legitimacy (Laufer, W.S, 2003). A study by (Braga Junior et al., 2019) shows that companies that uses green-washing and advertise the products that tends to be misleading can damage the image and lower the volume of sales, even extremely many of those products are withdrew from the market where it has been proven to be vague and irrelevant.

How do "Learning Organisation" play in businesses? Small businesses' strategic learning process face unique problems in the market, where the concept of learning organisation may have a limited context especially in small businesses (Wyer et al., 2000). Organizational learning may be affected by structure of businesses, especially when it is a large business there's a large amount of bureucratic feature (Argote, L. & Miron-Spektor, E., 2011). This logically implies to

two things, first bureaucratic feature may stop large corporations from falsely using green-washing and mislead societal perception, but secondly bureaucratic feature have a bad impact of organisational learning, where there will still be a chance that many corporation will not learn from the other firms that has withdrew because of green-washing.

But on the other side where green-orientation is legitimate for firms that offer franchises, with top management should establish a deal or agreement that both franchisor and franchisees should agree on (Lee et al., 2011). According to a couple studies in indonesia that is (Pratono et al., & Adi and Adawiyah 2019) the industry in indonesia are using eco-orientation because the value that was hold in the society is a material that springs from organisational learning. There are many tangible benefits gained from inter-organisational learning, as where firms are able to allocate their resources respectfully as there is a good market orientation and firm competitiveness (Pratono et al., 2019). An enviroment-oriented leadership that holds franchisor management are the biggest contributor to the Green orientation as where there's a large amount of franchisees that has to follow because of the agreement, marketing with eco green usually has better performance in the market because it was affected by consumers and other factors (Kim, M. & Stepchenkova, S., 2018).

The conclusion to this paper is that Green Orientation is good for a firm's performance and prespective where it affects consumers behavior positively, yet there are many firms that uses green-orientation to gain benefit but in the end proving to be green-washing where it gives negative impact to the firm's performance as it continues to deceive the public. But the existence of green-washing has made many firms whether big or small ones to do Organisation Learning as where the green-washing firms can be approved as one of the example that they should avoid and also should not imitate

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